

THE NATURAL GEOGRAPHICAL LOCATION OF THE JIZZAH OASIS AND ITS ROLE IN THE EMERGENCE OF ROCK PAINTING

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Annotation: In this article, an attempt was made to provide information about the territorial location and natural geographical location of the Jizzakh oasis in the sources.

Key words: Jizzakh, Ustrushona, rock paintings, Sirdarya, Zarafshan, Saykhonsoy, Pishag'arsoy.

Jizzakh oasis is located in the central part of Central Asia, most of which consists of deserts and steppes. The topography of the oasis is unique, the combination of mountain, sub-mountain, steppe and plain zones makes it unique. A large part of the country is occupied by the Mirzachol desert. It decreases from south-east to north-west. The part of the plain slopes to the north-west, and the average height is 250-300 m. Step-shaped plains rise towards the mountains from the north and northeast. This country is a region of Uzbekistan consisting of high and medium-altitude mountains, foothill oases, salt marshes and desert landscapes.[1]

The basis of the Jizzakh oasis is the Jizzakh region, which is located mainly in the Sangzor-Zomin region and is located in the central part of the Republic of Uzbekistan between the valleys of the Syrdarya and Zarafshan rivers. The total area of the region is 21.1 thousand km. is 4.5 percent of the total area of the republic. [2] The territory of the region is bordered by Mirzachol to the north and north-east, Nurota ridges to the west and north-west, and Turkestan and Morguzar mountains to the south. Zomin, Forish, Sh.Rashidov, Gallaorol, Yangiabod districts are included and the total land area is 17,000 km. constitutes These districts cover 42% of the total population, occupying 76.7% of the total area of Jizzakh region.[4]

The Mirzachol desert and the steppes on the northern slopes of the Turkestan mountains are rich in various natural resources for the development of animal husbandry. That is why, from the first stages of human society, the mountain valleys of the oasis were actively used by our ancestors. In terms of natural location, the comfort of the pastures, the abundance of different types of meadows and grasses for livestock allowed the livestock to multiply and fatten.

Scientists say that the characteristics of the geographical environment (soil, topography, flora, nature, heat, etc.) have a certain influence on the formation of the spiritual culture of the ethnos and its psyche. This is evident in the national characteristics, traditions, and customs of the peoples. [5] From this point of view, cattle breeding, dry farming and horticulture are mainly developed in the highlands and mountain regions of the Jizzakh oasis.

Dozens of mountain valleys belonging to the Morguzar range and the foothills of the Nurota mountain and the steppes and deserts adjacent to Mirzachol have long been famous for their grassy pastures. [6] Leguminous plants here include: wormwood, yantok, kovol, gulkhairi, alfalfa, wheat, chalov.) seasonal color from herbs: pea, chuchumoma, shivit, scallion (anzur

onion), kongurbosh, kogigul, rabbit, takasokol, spinach, tartamok, gozoyok, ivy, kozigul and dozens of types of lawn grass; from forest trees: juniper, hawthorn, maple, tricot, irgai, namatak, chia, wild almond, pistachio, olmurut, almond, etc. grew and were considered favorite fodder for livestock. The meat of sheep fed on mountain herbs and especially mountain juniper was distinguished by its delicacy and taste.

Due to these natural advantages, the Jizzakh oasis area, like other agricultural oases of Central Asia, has been intensively exploited since ancient times, and the materials proving it are also reflected in rock paintings. These antiquities show that this area also has a primitive history with traces of early humans.

Large villages in the Sangzor-Zomin region are mainly located in mountainous and mountainous areas, such as Moghol, Sartyuz, Aikor, Akgorgan, Bogishamol in the Sangzor valley, Gobdun, Kokbulok, Mirzabulok and other villages in the Gallaorol plain, Gallakaor, Gulshan, Chorvador, Amongeldi, Qizilqum, Karaabad. , and several villages such as Eshbulok were formed in the form of a strip in the foothills of Zomin and Nurota.[7]

Such a territorial organization of villages can be considered as a desire of the population to settle around large and small streams and rivers, in lands close to water, which are convenient for farming and gardening.

The terrain of the southern part of the Jizzakh oasis is made up of the Turkestan ridges and its western Morguzar and Chumkartov mountains (up to 2500-3000 m in height, 800 m in the Jizzakh part). Large, flat areas of the foothills and mountain areas of the oasis have developed dryland farming, mainly based on natural irrigation. Most of the mountain and sub-mountain regions are used as cattle pastures.

Mount Morguzar, which is considered the northern extension of the Turkestan ridge (average height is 1500-2000 m, and some peaks reach 2621 m), continues to the north and is separated from Nurota mountain through the Sangzor river valley. The narrowest part of the Sangzor valley is the Ilon Otdi gorge (120-130 m wide). Nurota mountain range is one of the mountains of average height, the highest peak reaches 2169 m.[9]

The climate of Jizzakh region is strongly continental, and the amount of annual precipitation in the plain part is around 200-350 mm. Due to the fact that the region consists of a plain, the north side is open, and the south side has mountains, cold air masses from the Arctic and Siberia stay here. As a result, the air temperature drops sharply in winter, the average temperature in January is -1-3 degrees, and the temperature reaches -30-35 degrees in cold days. On the contrary, this region is affected by thermal depression in summer, and the weather is dry and hot, the average temperature in July reaches +26 +28 degrees, sometimes it rises to +44 +46 degrees. precipitation increases towards the regions. The average annual rainfall on the northern slopes of the Turkestan mountain range is 600 mm, and on the slopes of the Nurota mountain range it is around 350-400 mm. Snow falls a lot in the mountains, its thickness reaches 0.50-1 m.

The main water source of the Jizzakh oasis is the Syrdarya, and the width of the river valley connecting to Mirzachol reaches 15 km. The banks of the river bed are steep, and remnant beds can be found in the valley. Some of these remnant valleys consist of lakes and marshes. The canals that supply water to Mirzachol, which occupies a large part of the Jizzakh oasis, start from Syrdarya. The water sources of the oasis are mainly rivers, streams, springs and springs that flow in a south-north direction. The main water source of the oasis is the Sangzor river.[11]

In terms of size, the main water source after the Sangzor River is the Zominsuv, formed by the confluence of the Kashkasuv, Koksuv and Kyzilmozor streams, which originate from the high peaks of the Turkestan ridge.

Khojamushkentsoy, which is considered the next water source, is formed by the collection of many spring waters in the village of Erganakli. Its average water flow is 9.7 m³. It is equal to a second, and it is considered very poor not only for the region of Khovos region, but also for Vohauch.

According to the structure of the land in Jizzakh oasis, light and typical gray soils are distributed. The south and south-west part of this area is mainly covered with flat thick loess sand and sand dunes. Lowlands (central and north-western part) are occupied by saline and saline soils. In the region, light-colored gray soils, grasslands and meadow-swamp soils are widespread in the region, and these lands are rich in various types of plants and groves. [12] Rivers such as Sangzor, Zominsuv, Qili, Ravotsoy, Saykhonsoy, Pishag'arsoy, Jaloyirsoy, Turkmansoy are water sources. the land structure is covered with fertile alluvial layers of the geological period. Also, the soil surface of these valleys is covered by a fertile, cultural agro-irrigation layer with a thickness of several centimeters to 2 meters, consisting of loam rock and sandy soil.

Dozens of mountain valleys belonging to the Morguzar range and the foothills of the Nurota mountain, the plains adjacent to Mirzachol have long been famous for their grassy pastures. [13] Here, leguminous plants include wormwood, yantok, kovol, gulkhairi, black alfalfa, wheat, chalov, gulsapsar, There are a lot of yarrow, syrigh, milkweed, carrack, ragwort, deer grass, and many others. In early spring, seasonal colored grasses, which are the first feed for livestock, grow dozens of types of peas, chuchumoma, shivit, scallion (anzur onion), scallions, scallions, rabbit, sedges, spinach, sedges, sedges, ivy, lambsquarters, and grasses. In the mountainous regions, juniper, hawthorn, maple, three-leaf clover, irgai, namatak, chia, wild almond, pistachio, olmarut, almond, etc. grew from the forest trees and were considered favorite fodder for cattle.[14] bushes and trees such as wild almonds, plums, apples, cherries, and saxophones grow. At an altitude of 2800-3000 m, the pasture region begins, where grasses such as juniper, sedge, sedge, and wild barley grow. In the groves along the Syr Darya, shrubs such as willow, willow, turangil, and sycamore grow.

Thus, it can be seen from the given information that the Jizzakh oasis has been rich in various natural resources for the development of different types of economy since ancient times. That is why, from the first stages of human society, the mountain valleys of the oasis were actively used by our ancestors. In terms of their natural location, the comfort of the pastures, the abundance of different types of meadows and grasses for farming and livestock allowed them to develop. This was the reason for the beginning of the territory of the Jizakh oasis from the earliest times.

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